

Application of Hard and Soft Acid-Base Theory in the Study of Mixed Ligand Thiocyanate-8-hydroxyquinoline Complexes of Bivalent Metal Ions of 3d-Transitional Series

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Hard and soft acid-base theory has been applied in the study of mixed ligand complexes of the type $[M(II)(NCS)_2(HQ)_2]$, where $M(II) = Mn^{2+}, Fe^{2+}, Co^{2+}, Ni^{2+}, Cu^{2+}$ or Zn^{2+} ; HQ = 8-hydroxyquinoline. The values of 'matching' for the N-end and S-end of thiocyanate have been calculated; higher values of matching obtained for the N-end indicate that thiocyanate is bonded to these metal ions (border line cases between hard and soft acids) through its N-end. Another parameter, 'matching constant' determined for these complexes, appears to be useful for showing relative metal-ligand bond strength. Its values lie in the sequence $Mn < Fe < Co < Ni < Cu > Zn$.

Correlations of 'matching constant' with atomic number, sum of the first two ionisation potentials, standard oxidation potentials and charge-size ratio of the metal ions have also been studied.

THIOCYANATE is an ambidentate ligand; it may coordinate to a metal ion through nitrogen, or through sulphur, or through nitrogen and sulphur both by means of bridging. The class 'a' metal ions (or, hard acids) are generally bonded to its nitrogen atom, whereas the class 'b' (or, soft acids) are bonded to the sulphur atom. A number of metal mixed ligand thiocyanate complexes with various nitrogen donors, such as nitro- or methylphenanthroline¹, pyridine, picolines and isoquinoline²⁻⁸ have been investigated. It appears that the mode of metal-thiocyanate bonding depends on the nature of metal ion and the substituent group present in the ligand, availability of d-orbitals in the ligand for back donation and steric requirements of the ligand.

Recently^{9,10} quantitative 'softness values' (defined latter in the text) of metal ions and donor atoms of ligands have been used as supporting evidence for establishing the structure of some thiocyanate complexes. The present work describes the application of quantitative aspects of hard and soft acid-base (H.S.A.B.) theory¹¹ in establishing the mode of metal-thiocyanate linkage in the mixed ligand thiocyanate 8-hydroxyquinoline (oxine, HQ) complexes of $Mn^{2+}, Fe^{2+}, Co^{2+}, Ni^{2+}, Cu^{2+}$ and Zn^{2+} .

Experimental

The metal nitrates/sulphates (AnalaR) were vacuum-dried before use. Potassium thiocyanate used was E. Merck (G.R.) reagent. 8-Hydroxyqui-

noline was recrystallised from ethanol, and the solvent was completely removed by drying.

Synthesis of mixed ligand thiocyanate-oxine complexes: The following general procedure was followed for preparing the complexes. The metal nitrate (sulphate in the case of Fe^{2+} and Cu^{2+}) and potassium thiocyanate were mixed in ethanolic solution in 1:2 mmol proportion. After stirring the reaction mixture for 2-2.5 h, the separated potassium nitrate (or sulphate) was filtered off and the filtrate was slowly evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure to obtain the metal thiocyanate. Subsequently, an excess of oxine solution in acetone was mixed with a freshly prepared solution of the metal thiocyanate (5 mmol). A colour change appeared initially; stirring for upto ~4 h resulted in the separation of solid mixed ligand complex which was filtered, washed and vacuum-dried.

The characterisation of the mixed ligand complexes on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance and magnetic measurements, and infrared and electronic spectral studies, has already been communicated¹². The present work describes the application of H.S.A.B. principles in establishing the metal-thiocyanate mode of linkage and certain correlations of the 'matching constant' (defined latter in the text) with the metal ion characteristics.

The quantitative 'softness values' of the metal ion (Lewis acid), E_n^+ , and ligand (Lewis base), E_m^+ , have been calculated for the various metal ions

studied, NCS(N-end), SCN (S-end) and oxine by using Klopman's equations^{1,3},

$$E_n^+ = IP_n - b^2(IP_n - EA_n) - \frac{X_s(C_s^n)^2(1-1/e)}{R_s} [q_s - 2b^2X_s(C_s^n)^2] \quad (1)$$

$$E_m^+ = IP_m - a^2(IP_m - EA_m) - \frac{X_r(C_r^m)^2(1-1/e)}{R_r} [q_r + 2b^2X_r(C_r^m)^2] \quad (2)$$

The terms used in equations (1) and (2) are, R_s and $R_r = (r + 0.82)$, where r = ionic radius (Pauling) of Lewis acid and base, respectively; $b^2 = 1/4$; $a^2 = 3/4$; $C_s^n = (C_r^m) = 1$; e = dielectric constant of the solvent; $X_s = q_s(q_s - 1)\sqrt{K}$; $X_r = q_r(q_r - 1)\sqrt{K}$; $k = 0.75$, and q_s and q_r are the charges on the Lewis acid and base, respectively; IP_n = ionisation potential and EA_n = electron affinity of the Lewis acid; IP_m = ionisation potential and EA_m = electron affinity of the Lewis base; R_r and R_s = atomic radius of the Lewis acid and base (atom), respectively. The values of IP , EA and R have been evaluated for an atom as a neutral species by simple modifications in known methods¹⁴⁻¹⁶. These 'softness values' have been used for calculating a quantity 'total softness', TE_{nm}^+ defined by the expression,

$$TE_{nm}^+ = E_n^+(M) + \Sigma E_m^+(NCS) + \Sigma E_m^+(L) \quad (3)$$

where, $E_n^+(M)$ = (total) softness of the metal ion, $\Sigma E_m^+(NCS)$ = total softness of NCS (N-end), $\Sigma E_m^+(L)$ = total softness of the ligand (HQ). A soft base is characterised by a higher value of E_n^+ and a soft acid by a lower value of E_n^+ . 'Since the 'softness values' of Lewis acids and bases increase in reverse directions, a better match for metal-ligand interaction will be expected by higher values of absolute difference between E_n^+ and E_m^+ . Thus, 'matching' E_{nm}^+ and another related parameter 'matching constant', ΔE_{nm}^+ may be defined as,

$$\text{Matching} = E_{nm}^+ = |E_n^+ - E_m^+| \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Matching constant} = \Delta E_{nm}^+ = |E_n^+ - E_m^+| + \text{c.f.s.e.} \quad (5)$$

where, c.f.s.e. = crystal field stabilisation energy. The 'matching' and 'matching constant' values of the mixed complexes have been calculated from equations (4) and (5), respectively and used to predict the possibility of thiocyanate to link up with the metal ions (M) through nitrogen end (M-NCS) or through sulphur end (M-SCN).

Results and Discussion

The calculated values of 'matching' of N-end (M-NCS) and S-end (M-SCN) of the thiocyanate ion; total 'softness values', c.f.s.e., and 'matching constant' of the mixed ligand complexes are reported in Table 1.

The analytical and spectral studies have revealed^{1,2} that the mixed ligand complexes are of the type $[M(II)(NCS)_2(HQ)_2]$, i.e. diisothiocyanato-bisoxinato-metal(II). The metal thiocyanate bonding is through the N-end of thiocyanate in these complexes. The positions of electronic spectral bands have been used also to calculate the c.f.s.e. values (Table 1).

A reference to Table 1 shows that the 'matching' values for M-NCS interaction are consistently greater than those for M-SCN for all the metal ions under study. It may, therefore, be concluded on the basis of a better match that these metal ions, which are borderline cases in terms of HSAB scale, prefer to link to the thiocyanate ion through its N-end. This is in full agreement with the conclusions drawn from the infrared spectral studies^{1,2}. The total 'softness values' for the complexes show a general decrease from Mn^{2+} to Cu^{2+} and then an increase at Zn^{2+} . The 'matching constant', however, appears to be a useful parameter of the strength of the metal-ligand bond as suggested by other workers¹⁰. The 'matching constant' values lie in the sequence $Mn < Fe < Co < Ni < Cu > Zn$, which is incidentally the natural order of stability (Irving-Williams series) of the complexes of these metal ions. The values of 'matching constants' may be correlated with metal ion characteristics. Plots of 'matching constants', ΔE_{nm}^+ of diisothiocyanato-bisoxinato-metal(II) complexes with the atomic numbers (Z), sum of the first two ionisation potentials (ΣI), standard oxidation potentials (E_H^0) and

TABLE 1—MATCHING OF THIOCYANATE ION, TOTAL SOFTNESS VALUES, C. F. S. E. AND MATCHING CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES $[M(II)(NCS)_2(HQ)_2]$

Metal	Matching of thiocyanate ion		Total softness value (TE_{nm}^+)	c. f. s. e. eV	Matching constant (ΔE_{nm}^+)
	NCS (N-end)	SCN (S-end)			
Mn	8.76	5.86	57.36	0	11.61
Fe	8.69	5.79	57.29	1.81	13.35
Co	7.40	4.50	56.00	4.26	14.51
Ni	8.39	5.49	56.99	5.83	16.07
Cu	7.55	4.65	56.15	9.82	20.22
Zn	7.07	4.17	55.67	0	9.92

charge/size ratios (q/r) of the metal ions are shown in Fig. 1. Increase in 'matching constants' is

ligand bond strength of complexes and compare very well with similar correlations between the formation constants of complexes in solution and the above metal ion characteristics.

Fig. 1. Variation of matching constant ($\Delta E_{nm}^{\ddagger}$) with (A) atomic number (Z), (B) sum of the first two ionisation potentials (ΣI), (C) standard oxidation potential (E_H°) and (D) charge/size ratio (q/r) of the 3d-metal ions.

associated with an increase in the values of these properties. These plots clearly indicate the utility of 'matching constants' in expressing the metal-

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References

1. A. SABATINI and I. BERTINI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 1025.
2. M. A. PORAI-KOSHITS and A. S. ANISHISHKIYA, *Krystallografiya*, 1958, 3, 676.
3. H. C. A. KING, B. KOROS and S. M. NELSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 5449; 1964, 4832.
4. M. A. PORAI-KOSHITS and G. N. TISCHENKO, *Krystallografiya*, 1959, 4, 239.
5. S. M. NELSON and T. M. SHEPHERD, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 813.
6. A. TURCO and C. PECILE, *Nature (London)*, 1961, 191, 66.
7. S. GURU, B. B. MAHAPATRA and B. PAUL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 337.
8. B. K. MOHAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 705.
9. P. P. SINGH and A. K. GUPTA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1978, 17, 1.
10. P. P. SINGH, S. K. SHRIVASTAVA and A. K. SHRIVASTAVA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, 42, 521, 533.
11. R. G. PEARSON, *J. Chem. Educat.*, 1968, 45, 581, 643.
12. K. MISHRA and M. C. SAXENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, communicated.
13. G. KLOPMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 223.
14. M. J. S. DEWAR and T. F. MARTIA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 91, 796.
15. R. T. SANDERSON, "Chemical Bond and Bond Energy", Academic Press, New York, 1971, p. 1920.
16. J. E. HUBEY, 'Inorganic Chemistry', Harper and Row, New York, 1972, pp. 71, 72.